

Workshop Description

Process Mapping and Process Improvement for Libraries Workshop

Overview

Every institution has many processes that allow it to function. Often those processes are less effective than they could be, and most institutions, if they were able to step back for a broader view, would benefit from improving them. Process reengineering is a set of techniques and skills that enable an institution to look at its processes, understand them, identify ways in which the processes could be improved, and set about implementing changes that will bring the desired results. This workshop trains participants in the techniques and skills of process reengineering in a unique, hands-on way. Using the Factory on a Desk-Top™, a simulated organization, participants explore real processes, design improvements, and measure results. They practice using skills for documenting processes, developing improvements, and implementing change. These skills are highly transferable to the institution because they have been learned experientially.

Learning Objectives

At the end of the workshop, participants will:

- Learn the basic techniques of business process mapping.
- Identify useful ways of looking at processes to identify potential improvements.
- Practice using process-reengineering techniques in a simulated organization.
- Develop a view of an organization as a set of interrelated systems that can be improved.
- Develop strategies for exploring process-improvement opportunities in their own institutions.
- Explore the skills required to implement process improvements in their own institutions.

Schedule

First Day (afternoon)

1:00–5:00 Hands-on introduction to process mapping and process improvement using the Factory on a Desk-Top™

5:15–6:45 Dinner

7:00–9:00 Discussion of library processes

Second Day

8:30–12:30 Practice using process mapping and process improvement for library operations

Appalachian College Association Central Library

Tony Token Program

What Is the Tony Tokens Program?

The Tony Token Program is part of [the New TiLTS grant](#) from CLIR (Council for Library and Information Resources). Each library is encouraged to identify services that it could provide to other ACA libraries. For example, if you have book-repair expertise on your staff, you may offer this service to other libraries. Or you may develop a New TiLTS project proposal to create a service center that provides a service needed by several libraries. Be creative!

Tony Tokens are vouchers that can be exchanged for services from other participating ACA libraries. A Tony Token is valued at 30 minutes. Each library sets the charge for its services. If a library has a service you need, contact the library's service coordinator and negotiate the details and charge, payable in Tony Tokens.

Dianne Schaffer of the ACA Central Library staff will track the exchange of Tony Tokens and maintain the list of available services and service coordinators. The New TiLTS Steering Committee assists Dianne with the program. If you have any questions about the Tony Token Program or New TiLTS grant, please contact Anne Chase (anne_chase@berea.edu).

How Are Tony Tokens Earned?

- Participate in a Process Mapping and Process Improvements for Libraries workshop—25 Tony Tokens
- Submit a list of services for the program—25 Tony Tokens
- Develop a New TiLTS project—50 Tony Tokens
- Provide services to other ACA libraries. Each library sets its own charge

What Services Are Available?

The following libraries are willing to share their expertise and services with other ACA libraries. If you are interested in a service, contact the appropriate service coordinator to negotiate the charge, which is payable in Tony Tokens. Each library sets the Tony Token charge for its services. Dianne Schaffer (diannes@acaweb.org) will arrange for the transfer of Tony Tokens from one library's account to another.

<i>TONY TOKENS - BVAIABLE SERVICES</i>	<i>LIBRARY</i>	<i>Service Coordinator</i>
Voyager Acquisitions Training	Berea	Calvin Gross
Organization of archival materials (analog)	Bethany	Laura Slocum
Docutek ERes training (including setup and on-going use)	Brevard	Mike McCabe
Dbase Usage Stats Collection Services	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Digital scanning of microforms	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Digitizing audio/video	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Endeavor bulk record importing	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Endeavor E-reserves (including linking with ACA proxy password protections)	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Endeavor ad-hoc reports using Microsoft Access	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Multi-media training	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Process mapping software (R&D, training or service)	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Serials Solution Conversions	Bryan	Laura Kaufmann
Collection Development in U.S. History, Native American Studies, Latin American History, and Appalachian Studies	Campbellsville	John Burch
Macro writing for OCLC's Connexion	Emory & Henry	Lorraine Abraham
Mending of materials	Emory & Henry	Lorraine Abraham
CD/DVD duplication (mass disc duplication and label printing)	Lee	Don Smeeton
Multimedia development (3D Studio Max, Macromedia Director, Adobe Premiere, Adobe Aftereffects, Macromedia Freehand, Macromedia Flash)	Lee	Don Smeeton
PERL programming (useful for batch manipulation of MARC records and XML)	Lee	Don Smeeton
Preservation for Special Collections (consulting)	Lee	Don Smeeton
Web design technologies such as CSS, JavaScript, PHP, Perl, and MySQL	Lee	Don Smeeton

Digital Library of Appalachia project implementation	Lincoln Memorial	Donna Bible
Student training for archival and publishable digital documents	Lincoln Memorial	Donna Bible
Cataloging 3-D objects (toys, etc.)	Lindsey Wilson	Phil Hanna
Medical/health/nursing (anything)	Pikeville	Susan Suess
Multi Media	Union	Tara Cooper
System migration	Union	Tara Cooper

Warren Wilson College Library New TiLTS Project Final Report

From Assembly Line to Craft Shop: Reorganizing Student Workers in Technical Services at Warren Wilson College

Goals

While most academic libraries use student workers, Warren Wilson College is unusual in two respects. First, our college has a mandatory work program in which all students, regardless of financial need, aptitude, or interest, are required to work on one of over 100 work crews on campus. Second, unlike many college libraries, which select their student workers, our library is assigned 20 to 24 students, mostly first-year students, by the Work Program Office. Our library is in competition to retain our student workers, who often prefer crews that take them outdoors, require physical activity, allow them social interaction, and complement their career goals. The library has experienced very low retention rates of student workers, unlike other college libraries, where student workers remain in place throughout most of their academic careers.

In our library, technical services comprises two departments: acquisitions/collection development and cataloging. We depend on student workers to serve paraprofessional functions, but the vast majority of the tasks in both departments is detail oriented and repetitive, which often cause the typical eighteen-year-old to perceive them as tedious and unsatisfying. Prior to the project, the turnover rate among our student workers was almost 100 percent each year, or even each semester. This situation presented tremendous challenges as we invested heavily in repeated training and depended on a highly inexperienced student crew, whose skill level and commitment were low.

In the past, the five to seven student workers in technical services were assigned to the cataloging or acquisitions departments, where they performed tasks specific to the operations of that department. There was little crossover in student jobs between the departments, and as a result, few of our students understood or appreciated the big picture of what went on in technical services.

The goals of the New TiLTS project were to address these issues (high turnover, low skill, low commitment, and job fragmentation) by creating a learning as well as a production environment. We wanted to develop a crew of more committed and more-skilled student workers. We wanted to move away from the assembly-line model of work toward a craft shop model, where each worker is responsible for an item from the time it is received from a vendor to the time it is shelved and ready for patron use.

Strategies

New Workflow

We combined the cataloging and acquisitions crews to form a new technical services crew. This integration created a more seamless work experience, so that work flowed more fluidly between the two departments and student workers were able to see the interconnectedness of the processes in technical services as well as the value of their work to the library as a whole. Combining the crews also provided a larger array of work. One of the students, who had worked in the acquisitions department before the integration observed, “I like cataloging and acquisitions being in the same department now. It gives a great deal more variety to my day.”

Integrating our crews enabled us to redesign and streamline the workflow between the departments. The two librarians have enjoyed the increased opportunity to collaborate and consult with each other. Our new workflow is outlined in Appendix 1.

New Procedures

Each worker is now responsible for an item from the time it is received from a vendor to the time it is shelved and ready for patron use. Each item is marked with a color-coded flag (e.g., yellow flags for student A, green for student B) as it proceeds through the process on specially marked book trucks, purchased with New TiLTS grant monies. When the item is ready, the student initials the bar code and stamps the date due slip with a message such as “Prepared by (name).” At various points in the process, the two librarians provide quality control checks and feedback to the student workers and track and post errors on a white board, also purchased with New TiLTS funds. This system has built accountability, ownership, and pride, and resulted in higher-quality work, enhanced worker satisfaction, and improved retention rate, as indicated in our assessment below.

Training

We provided three kinds of skill training:

1. Basic skills, which enabled students to perform the daily and routine work in technical services, such as materials handling and processing. These included bar coding, security stripping, assigning Cutter numbers, applying plastic jackets and spine reinforcements, call number labeling, stamping, and catalog checking.
2. Advanced skills, which were taught to everyone in technical services but were performed only occasionally. Although not everyone had the opportunity to apply these skills on the job, they were useful skills and we wanted everyone in technical services to have at least a basic knowledge of these areas. Examples of advanced skills included book mending, basic HTML or Web authoring, working with vendors, and working with invoices and budgets.
3. Value-added skills, which were perks we offered everyone who worked with us. These skills were useful for finding information for the students’

research and coursework and for lifelong learning. Value-added skills included power searching on our local SIRSI catalog, advanced searching on WorldCat, finding articles in magazines and journals, and evaluating the quality of information retrieved.

We developed a syllabus for teaching these three types of skills and gave exercises and tests to measure the effectiveness of our training program. See the section on Assessment for a discussion. Certificates of completion, which were awarded to students who completed their training in the basic skills, were well received and gave the students a sense of accomplishment.

We offered frequent refreshments and small gifts as incentives and morale boosters, funded in part by the New TiLTS grant. At the end of the fall semester, we had a holiday party and are planning an end-of-semester celebration.

Assessment

Error Tracking

We developed a chart for monitoring the numbers and types of errors, so that we could provide more relevant feedback to our student workers and identify areas where further training might be needed. The error-tracking chart, posted on a board purchased with New TiLTS grant funds, is summarized below:

Month and Year	No. of Errors
September 2004	52
October 2004	26
November 2004	37
December 2004	23

See Appendix 2 for the complete chart, which records errors made by the students during the processing of an average of 270 items each month.

By the end of September 2004, the students had completed basic skill training. Their higher skill level is reflected in the smaller number of errors in October. Although the number of errors increased in November, much of this increase is attributable to an individual student who was experiencing academic and personal difficulties and who dropped out of Warren Wilson College at the end of the semester.

Accomplishments

The error chart caused some of our students to feel that we placed undue emphasis on errors over their growing competence. So, in the spring semester, we changed our focus from errors to special accomplishments. We feel that this approach emphasizes positive reinforcements for our skilled crew by recognizing extraordinary group and individual work behaviors. We also provided a category for students to report their own accomplishments and problems (see Appendix

3). To share a sense of progress, we posted monthly statistics on the number of items added. Both charts were well received. One student wrote that the accomplishment chart was “awesome.”

Training

On the whole, the students scored well on the exercises and tests. They appreciated the basic and advanced training we provided because they saw the relevance of these skills to their daily tasks. To our surprise, however, some of them expressed negative opinions about the academic “feel” of the exercises and tests in a work setting. This opinion was exacerbated by the perception that students in other departments of the library were not required to meet these expectations. Overall, the value-added skills we intended as a perk for our crew were not well received by the first-year students who constituted the majority of our crew. One of the reasons was their perception that our training duplicated other library instruction sessions required as part of their first year seminars.

Work Program Evaluations

At the end of the fall semester, the librarians completed a work performance evaluation for each student. In these evaluations, we confirmed that all our students had a good understanding of what needed to be done and that they could work fairly independently by the end of the first semester.

The students completed work program supervisor evaluations of the librarians. In their evaluations, the students indicated that they wanted more positive reinforcements and more frequent recognition of their achievements. However, we found inconsistencies and contradictions in these evaluations. Because the evaluations have been completed only once, cumulative and comparative data are not yet available. The forms used for these evaluations were the same for all work crews on campus and were not specifically geared toward the library setting. They did not address issues we were most concerned to emphasize.

Writing Prompts

More useful to us were the periodic writing prompts we administered. So far, our students have completed eight of these brief pieces, in which they shared with us their opinions and suggestions on a variety of matters. These prompts enabled us to take the pulse of our student workers and provided timely feedback that guided us in making corrections or adjustments as necessary.

The students’ responses to the first prompt clearly indicated their initial confusion at the beginning of the New TiLTS project. One wrote, “I feel rather as though I’ve been thrown headfirst into the book processing. I have no feel for the overall sequence or process, which makes things a bit difficult.” By the second prompt, however, they had achieved a clearer understanding of the workflow and job expectations. One of the students noted about her learning, “I’ve come to understand the Dewey Decimal System in far more depth than I thought possible. I’ve also learned a lot about searching for books, which will be helpful

with projects.” In early October, the students requested that they be allowed to listen to music as they worked, a request that we granted after establishing some guidelines. In the fifth writing prompt, they told us that they appreciated having the music and they felt the guidelines were fair. The sixth prompt showed that they found the value added skills useful and they appreciated having the opportunity to work on their research, although they were not enthusiastic about the training. Toward the end of the fall semester, a certain weariness set in, as students told us that they were tired. On a 5-point scale, they rated themselves an average of 4 on effort and 3.2 on job satisfaction. This was a low point for us: one of the students left school, and another, an art major, chose to join the ceramics crew. These two departures, together with the graduation of a third student, meant that we had lost 50 percent of our crew.

However, the spring semester saw a clear turnaround. The smaller crew proved to be advantageous, and the students seemed to be infused with a new enthusiasm for the work. Writing prompt number 8, completed in February, returned such comments as, “I feel good about doing my work. In general, I am more motivated than last semester. I will try to maintain this willingness to perform the job.” Another student wrote, “I feel very confident in everything that I do here.”

The reduced crew size did not present a problem in productivity as the students worked diligently to process the items that had accumulated over the winter holidays and handled the increased workload typical of spring semesters at Warren Wilson College. In fact, the students preferred a smaller crew, writing, “Keep it this size,” “Three or four people is the perfect amount,” and “We don’t have to worry about not having enough books to process.” The smaller crew size also resulted in a less noisy and crowded workspace and a more orderly work environment, elements that some students had commented on in the first semester.

Retention

We began the year and the New TiLTS project with six student workers. In September, one of our student workers had to withdraw from the crew when her home was severely damaged by the remains of Hurricanes Frances and Ivan. At the end of the fall semester, our crew was further reduced when a second student dropped out and a third left to join the ceramics crew.

As described under Writing Prompts above, we began the spring semester with a much smaller but reenergized crew. All three students are performing well, and two have indicated that they planned to return to the technical services crew next year. The third will join another crew.

Of the original six student workers, we expect to retain two. While this may not seem impressive, it represents a marked success for us and is a significant improvement over our near-zero rate of previous years.

Conclusion

We are delighted with the crew morale this semester. The students have achieved one of the main goals of the project: they have developed a sense of job ownership, unit responsibility, and workgroup pride. Our students understand the big picture of technical services. We are also pleased with an efficiency we had not anticipated: our three-person crew is able to produce as much work as was done by five to seven students before our departmental crews were combined. Moreover, the quality of the work is consistently higher than it was before the implementation of this project.

On the basis of our experiences with the New TiLTS project, we plan to refine many of the initiatives we began this year, including the following:

- Syllabus
- Workflow and color-coded flag system
- Accountability and personalization with the "Prepared by _____" stamps
- Periodic writing prompts
- Basic training for new students, with mentoring by returning students
- Award certificates for completion of basic training
- Advanced training
- Error-tracking chart
- Accomplishment chart
- Periodic refreshments and gifts

We are pleased with the outcomes of our New TiLTS project. It has given us many valuable insights into instructing, supervising, and working with student workers.

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Appendix 1: New Workflow

Appendix 2: Error Chart

SKILL	Wk3	Wk4	Wk5	Wk6	Wk7	Wk8	Wk9	Wk10	Wk11	Wk12	Wk13	Wk14	Wk1 5	Wk1 6
When request is received, check catalog and netLibrary.														
<i>Search Books in Print.</i>														
When order is placed, notify requester.														
When items arrive, unpack, put on truck, and match order slips with items.														
Assign flags and check workflows.														
Assign Cutter number. Bar code and tag for security. Put on proper shelf.	7	2	5	5	6	7	7	2	14	2	2	4	5	4
Check book, order slip, and spine label. If mismatch, return item to Mei.														
Affix spine label.		2		2		1		1						
Apply plastic jackets or spine reinforcements.			1		1									
Use special processing and labels for AV items.		1	2											
Stamp book and affix	2	2		1	1					10		1		1

date due slips (if not reference. book).														
Stamp "Prepared by____" and write your name on date due slip or initial in pencil by bar code.	3	8	2	7	1		2	2			2			
Final check by Joy														
Shelve books in new books section														
Notify requester that item is ready.														
Totals	12	15	10	15	9	8	9	5	14	12	14	5	5	5

Appendix 3: Special Accomplishments Chart[‡]
A Record of Extraordinary Accomplishments by the Technical Services Crew

	Wk2	Wk3	Wk4	Wk5	Wk6	Wk7	Wk8	Wk9	Wk10	Wk11	Wk12	Wk13	Wk14	Wk1 5	Wk1 6
Group															
Time cards	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*							
Shelf reading				☺											
Punctuality/attendance	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*							
Interpersonal skills															
Individual															
Busy and focused			F,J, Z	F,J, Z	F,J, Z	F,J, Z	F,J, Z								
Provides advice/assistance	J														
Communication	Z	Z					J								
Innovative and appropriate approaches															
Initiative							J								
Adaptation to changes		F													
Problem solving	F	J,Z		J											
Learning and skill development															
Workspace and equipment															

[‡] This chart is still in progress.

SELF-REPORTING: ACCOMPLISHMENTS

SELF-REPORTING: PROBLEMS

Bethany College and Wheeling Jesuit University Review of Technical Services

Summary

To reduce costs and improve process efficiencies, the number of manual steps that staff perform when using system tools, paper, and handling items needs to be minimized. Recommendations include (1) purchasing materials through library vendors so as to leverage discounts, (2) taking advantage of offline processing options, such as producing labels that are offered free or at a nominal cost, and (3) implementing automated offline cataloging processes such as OCLC's PromptCat. By receiving full OCLC MARC records, professionals are relieved of copy cataloging tasks. As a result, they are able to perform more complex tasks, such as processing gift, archive, and digital collections; evaluating statistics and services; and creating reports.

PromptCat benefits

- OCLC MARC records arrive with your local data, and holdings already added.
- Offline automated processes eliminate the need to search, export, and confirm record is a correct match.
- Records sometimes arrive before materials do.
- More than 20 material vendors partner with OCLC to offer the service.

Consult your regional service provider, who could conduct a feasibility and cost analysis for incorporating PromptCat service into your workflow.

Streamline the efficiency of ordering processes by utilizing existing acquisitions tools or system modules. Although current WJU accounting processes require some tracking of materials with paper, replace shelf list cards, ledgers, and writing on inside covers of books with notes, for example, recording the OCLC record number. According to National Center for Education Statistics (NCES), 100 percent of the libraries in West Virginia have reported that they are automated. This reinforces the assumption that shelf list and associated cards are unnecessary. Although the number of academic institutions that still maintain shelf lists is uncertain, all WV academic libraries reported that they provide an electronic catalog that includes the library's holdings on campus [Table 12A, p 43]. The data are reported by NCES, which collects information biennially from about 3,700 postsecondary institutions (Carey, Nancy, Natalie M. Justh, Jeffrey W. Williams. (2003). U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics. Academic Libraries: 2000. 2004-317. NCES: Washington, D.C.)

Track the receipt and status of orders online by using a centralized tool such as SIRSI's Workflow. The training manuals provide exercises to help staff become familiar with the numerous features and tools.

Reduce the amount of time that it takes for materials to be processed by applying jacket covers only to materials that are frequently circulated. A study comparing electronic and print book usage at Louisiana State University found that only 30 percent of print and 20 percent of electronic books were used. The circulation of both formats followed the academic year. University press e-books

garnered a smaller share of accesses relative to title count than did those of commercial publishers. The most popular subjects in both formats were library science, literature, economics, education, sociology, political science, medicine, and mathematics. Popular e-book-only titles were biology and technology; popular print-only were philosophy and American history. (Christianson, Marilyn, and Marsha Aucoin. 2005. Electronic or Print Books: Which Are Used? *Library Collections, Acquisitions and Technical Services*. 29(March): 71-81)

(Consultant recommended including circ data. The following was added by WJU. A Sirsi report of WJU's past 12 month circulation revealed that the Library of Congress classes B, D, H, and P comprised 68% of circulation with other categories having few circulations. These would be the areas of philosophy, psychology, religion, history, social sciences, and language and literature. Sirsi title use report detailing number of transactions on the B category for the past 12 months revealed the following circulation: 6 uses on 1 item, 4 uses on 3 items, 3 uses on 11 items, 2 uses on 87 items, and 1 use on 925 items. Sirsi itemlist report showed fewer than 1% of titles (1,489) have circulated more than 10 times since automation in 1996.)

Eliminate tracking of bibliographic data on inside of books and pieces of paper by inputting information in the SIRSI system. The cataloger can delete temporary information during the quality control check. To ensure quality control, catalogers need to complete final check and verify correctness of call numbers, complete record is in SIRSI system and that processing and labels are correct. Eliminate manually compiling statistics by utilizing the variety of statistical reports that SIRSI generates, including group reports, and a list of line items that can be e-mailed to faculty.

The following chart illustrates institutional resources and technical services practices and processes for Wheeling Jesuit University and Bethany College. The chart is an attempt to quickly communicate recommended processes, gaps, and opportunities to improve efficiency by utilizing automating tools that may help

- reduce the number of times an item is handled more than once;
- reduce the number of online copy cataloging processes;
- reduce the number and types of tasks associated with processing;
- decrease the amount of time needed to generate statistical reports; and
- increase the number of items processed in backlogs.

As a result of this workflow analysis, the following modifications in the processes are recommended:

- Entries displayed in PINK represent processes identified as opportunities.
- Entries displayed in RED represent processes could be eliminated
- Entries in GREEN represent processes that could be modified to improve efficiency

Wheeling Jesuit University			Bethany College	
Staff			Staff	
87 FTE		Faculty	60	
Yes		Full time cataloger also performs other duties	Yes	
Yes		Full time acquisitions staff	No (Director performs tasks)	
No		Technical services staff assistants	Yes, two part-time	
Yes, intermittent		Student workers	Yes, three days a week	
Yes, two		Circulation staff	Student workers rotating shifts	
No		Archivist	Yes	
Special projects			Special projects	
No		Butterfly garden, art collection, children's corner, Pulitzer prize collection, light reading collection	Yes	
Yes		Book sale weekly	No	
No		Book sale annually	Yes	
Materials			Materials	
153,590		Number of volumes	122,107	
Yes <i>Will continue to use Amazon for certain items</i>		Purchases most orders from Amazon.com	No	
No		Purchases most orders from Library material vendors	Yes	
\$48,600		Purchasing budget	\$64,000	
>2,000		Number of Archive materials	>225,000+	

<i>Few</i>		Archive materials cataloged	<i>Yes</i>	
Yes, small		Children's collection	Yes, extensive	
Approximately >1 %		Percent of collection AV materials	Approximately >4%	
Yes, from consortia		E-book collection	Yes, from consortia	
Yes		Duplicates CDs that accompany monographs	No Will start	
Yes		Standing orders	By series type: NY Times best sellers, Newberry, Caldecott, American Library series	
No <i>We have gifts and donations but not extremely large</i>		Large Gifts/donations	Yes	
No		Digitized collections	In process	
Budget			Budget	
\$48,600		Materials	\$64,000	
No		Book endowment	Yes	
System tools			System tools	
Yes		SIRSI	Yes	
Yes		Uses SIRSI Acquisition module-WorkFlows	No	
<i>Yes but it is not the cataloger's job duty</i>		Uses Serials Solution	Yes	
Yes		Collection completely barcoded	No	
No Will begin a trial period and evaluate promptcat	Material vendors offer discounts and order OCLC MARC records via PromptCat	Orders most materials from library material vendor	Yes	

No		Faculty selects titles from Books in Print BIP	Yes	
Yes <i>sometimes</i>		Faculty selects titles from Amazon	Minimal	
Yes		Faculty selects titles from Journals	Yes	
Yes <i>Faculty submit orders as they wish</i>	Faculty submit order requests via Acquisition module	Faculty either completes print order card or sends email to acquisitions clerk		
No		Faculty send email to Library Director	Yes	
Yes		Acquisition clerk places orders	No	
No		Director places order	Yes	
Gifts/donations			Gifts/donations	
No		Bibliography created first	Yes	Send donor letter of acknowledgment
Yes		Assistant staff searches SIRSI before <i>librarian</i> decides to retain gift	Yes	
Yes		Acquisition clerk searches and exports MARC record from OCLC to create on order record in SIRSI	No	
No <i>Cataloger double checks that record is correct, updates and edits in Sirsi</i>		When item arrives cataloger searches and exports record from OCLC and imports into SIRSI	Yes	
Yes		Add holdings to OCLC	Yes	
Retrieve PromptCat file and export OCLC records which already includes local data, and import into system. Holdings are already added.				
Yes		Student workers process materials	Yes	
Yes <i>Will continue to</i>		Apply jacket covers to all materials	No	

<i>cover all</i>				
No		Apply reinforcement tape to materials	Yes	
Yes		Circulation handles reserves	No	
Yes <i>shelflist has been closed</i>	Track orders online through SIRSI Workflow	Shelflist maintained	No	
Library of Congress		Classification	Dewey Decimal	
<i>Yes, but uses sirsi validate</i>		Accepts authority control in record as is	Not always	
Yes		E-book MARC records loaded into SIRSI	In process	
Occasional		Library assistants enter brief on order records	No	
Yes		Shelf space constraints	Yes	
Yes <i>Change from 4 times to 1 time</i>	<i>and we changed the stamp</i>	Stamp reference book with "Reference" stamp	No	
<i>Yes, assistant will continue to double-check what cataloger enters as call number and some record data. Cataloger will spot check only.</i>		Assistant performs quality control (call number, data)	No	
No		Assistant creates call number label	Yes	
Yes <i>Will continue to manually track discards but will develop sirsi report to track titles, volumes, added</i>	SIRSI compiles statistical reports	Manually compiles statistical reports	No, <i>uses Sirsi reports</i>	

NOTICE: Christina at WJU edited this consultant report including making changes and deletions for clarification. Changes are italicized.

Bluefield College Technical Services & Circulation Cooperation - Workflow Before Analysis

Previous cataloging workflow, again with minimal help from student workers and other library staff. Again, the transportation of materials between floors lengthens and complicates the process.

Bluefield College Technical Services and Circulation Cooperation - Workflow After Analysis

Streamlining the Management of Overdue Materials at Montreat College

Measure	End of Fall 2004	End of Spring 2005	Percentage of Change
Number of students with overdue items	42	128	*
Number of overdue items	141	577	*
Items not returned	49	24	- 51.0%
Students with items not returned	21	9	-57.0 %
Support staff time	32.1 hours	42.5 hours	+3.23%
Professional staff time	<u>19.0 hours</u>	<u>02.5 hours</u>	-86.8%
Total Time	51.1 hours	45.0 hours	-11.9%
Turnaround time for shelving items	4.6 days	1.2 days	-73.9%
Items returned at the end of semester	287 **	252 **	-12.2%

* Reports for the fall term are incomplete.

** More items were checked out during the spring term. After the library began to send monthly overdue notices, students began to return overdue items to the library during the semester rather than waiting until the end of the semester.

Improving the Shelving of Items at Bryan College: Workflow and Best Practices

Process Maps

Former Shelving Process

Returned books checked in at circulation desk.

Books sorted and placed by circulation desk workers in call number order on cart at circulation desk.

Trained shelver takes cart to second floor for shelving.

Shelver retrieves books from tables and carrels and places them on cart.

Shelver begins shelving books. Patrons place books they have used at the end of the row from which they took the book. Library shelvers watch for such books and reshelve them as they perform their normal shelving duties.

New Shelving Process

Returned books checked in at circulation desk

Books sorted and placed by circulation desk workers in call number order on cart at circulation desk.

Trained shelver takes cart to second floor for shelving.

Shelver retrieves books from tables and carrels and adds them to the cart for reshelving. During the transition to the new process, shelvers still watch for books reshelved by patrons at the ends of the rows.

Shelvers reshelve books found on second floor return carts.

Former Procedure for Training Shelvers

Some student workers were identified to be trained as shelvers.

Verbal, one-on-one explanation given by librarian of Dewey Decimal Classification system and call numbers.

Student shelve asked to rearrange a cart of books in proper call number order.

Cart checked by librarian. Any errors corrected and explained to shelve.

Shelve takes cart of books to shelving area. Books are shelved spine-down by new shelve so that librarian can check for correct order.

If book is incorrectly shelved, librarian makes a note of it and informs the new shelve.

If all books are shelved properly, the student is considered a regular shelve.

New Procedure for Training Shelves

All circulation desk workers receive shelving training.

Verbal, one-on-one explanation given by librarian of Dewey Decimal Classification system and call numbers.

Shelving trainee completes Dewey Easy computer program.

Student shelve asked to rearrange a cart of books in proper call number order.

Cart checked by librarian. Any errors are corrected and explained to shelve.

Shelve takes cart of books to shelving area. Books are shelved spine-down by new shelve so that librarian can go through and check for correct order.

If book is incorrectly shelved, librarian makes a note of it and informs the new shelve.

If all books are shelved properly, the student is considered a trained shelve.

Reflections: Shelving Best Practice Suggestions

As part of this study, consideration was given to the incorporation of best practices gleaned through a survey of sister ACA libraries and a review of two

benchmark shelving projects at other libraries.* As we planned this project, some of these practices became part of our new approach to shelving. Others are still under consideration.

1. A 24-hour turnaround time for reshelving books is a desirable goal.
2. We now direct patrons to return books they have used while in the library to nearby carts.
3. Staff gather books used in the library from tables and carrels and place on return carts.
4. We have not initiated the step of returning in-library-use books to the circulation desk for scanning to record use. A recommendation is that we initiate this step in order to register use of such items, providing a useful statistic at budget time.
5. We now use the Dewey Easy** program to train shelvees.
6. We frequently shelve books collecting in the carts at the circulation desk rather than waiting for the carts to fill completely. All circulation desk workers were trained to perform shelving, thus eliminating the need to wait for a trained shelvee to report for duty.
7. It is difficult for weekend workers to perform shelving duty as it requires that they be absent from the circulation desk. Often, they are the only workers on duty at those times.
8. Further thought should be placed upon requiring regular (i.e., more than once per year) shelf reading of high-use Dewey areas in our library (e.g., the 200s and the 800s).
9. For high-use areas, we may want to consider asking summer regular staff to perform additional shelf reading as needed.
10. Produce an Inventory of Basic Skills to facilitate training of circulation desk workers and shelvees.
11. Consider training and appointing a student worker as a shelving team leader.
12. Consider incentives/motivators for shelving and shelf-reading workers.

*Creelan, Marilee, Rebecca R. Fehrenbach, and Jacqueline A. Rodgers. 1998. A Benchmark for Quality Shelving: Weaving Our Way through the Stacks. Unpublished. Medical College of Georgia: Augusta, Ga. Available at <http://www.mcg.edu/Library/MLA/Index.html>.

Report on Shelving Process, January-May 1999. University of Virginia Library. Available at <http://www.lib.virginia.edu/mis/benchmarking/bench-shortrpt.html>.

** The computer training program for shelvees is available as either Dewey Easy or LC Easy. Users may download a trial version. For more information on these products, go to <http://librarytools.com/>

Guidelines for Enclosing Books and Works on Paper in Small Library Special Collections

Most small libraries do not have professional conservators or rare-book librarians on staff, nor do they have the resources necessary to routinely contract for such services. There are several low-cost strategies that small libraries can undertake to preserve materials in their special collections. One such strategy is to place fragile materials in protective enclosures. These guidelines focus on the creation of preservation enclosures that are appropriate for paper-based special collections in small libraries.

Selection for Enclosure

Enclosing every item in a special collection is usually neither affordable nor necessary. Librarians should select the items for which the cost of enclosure provides the greatest benefit. First consideration is typically given to the following:

- manuscript material
- materials printed before 1850 that are in deteriorating condition, especially leather bindings
- works with vellum binding
- works with brittle paper (especially works printed between 1860 and 1900)
- first editions of important works
- works with attribution value (signed works, presentation copies, books with significant marginalia)
- works of special aesthetic value (fine bindings, papers, illustrations, etc.)
- works of high intellectual value because of association with significant people, places, or events
- materials of high monetary value
- scarce works generally not available in reprint

Preparation for Enclosure

Work with small groups of similar materials to create enclosures. This will facilitate efficient workflow and standard practice. Depending on the condition of the item to be enclosed, some preparation may be required before creating an enclosure.

- Restore the integrity of item as far as possible. Place detached pages in the proper order.
- Flatten folded paper if possible without causing damage. Undertake archival-quality paper repairs as possible to allow for readability. It is usually not necessary to repair every tear.
- Remove harmful fasteners such as staples or paper clips.
- Remove acidic inserts such as bookmarks, clippings, or pressed flowers. Place these in a buffered, acid-free envelope or another enclosure (see below) if appropriate to retain for collection.

- Dust, if possible, or otherwise lightly clean soiled items without soft media (e.g., charcoal, pastel, pencil). Clean only insofar as needed to remove particulate matter that could cause abrasion or to allow for readability.

Enclosures

Select an enclosure based on the item's format, medium, condition, and anticipated use. Enclosure materials are permanent and durable, as defined by ANSI/NISO standards.

Material type	recommended enclosure	enclosure characteristics
Book Small book or pamphlet	Tuxedo box	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ .044" or similar thickness acid-free low-lignin/lignin-free boxboard. ✓ Grain of box board runs parallel to book spine. ✓ Tongue-and-slot closure. ✓ Round corners for safer handling ✓ Custom-made to closely fit a specific book. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
Book Large, heavy book	Phase box	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ .044" or similar thickness acid-free low-lignin/lignin-free boxboard. ✓ Grain of boxboard runs parallel to book spine. ✓ Tied closure. ✓ Round corners for safer handling ✓ Custom-made to closely fit a specific book. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
Book High-value, very fragile	Clamshell box	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ All materials used in construction must be chemically stable. ✓ Buffered material used for acidic paper. Do not use buffered materials with works that contain dyes or pigments sensitive to high alkalinity (such as some types of photographs and textiles.) ✓ Custom-made to closely fit a specific book. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents ✓ Typically prepared by professional bookbinder.
Flat document Stable print material Content viewed on two sides	Mylar encapsulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 4 mil Mylar ✓ Air space ✓ Not suitable for pencil, charcoal, pastel, chalk, or graphite media ✓ Round corners for safer handling

Material type	recommended enclosure	enclosure characteristics
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Store document in acid-free folder or storage box. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
<p>Flat document Single stable print document stored in acid-free folders or other storage</p>	<p>Paper L-folder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Acid-free buffered paper ✓ 20# paper for durable items, 80# paper for items needing slightly more support. ✓ Do not use buffered materials with works that contain dyes or pigments sensitive to high alkalinity (such as some types of photographs and textiles.) ✓ Not suitable for media that can be smudged, such as charcoal or pastels. ✓ Notch in top layer for easier handling ✓ Store document in acid-free folder or storage box. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
<p>Flat document Stable print material Content viewed on two sides, access to original retained</p>	<p>Mylar L-folder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 4 mil Mylar ✓ Open on two sides ✓ Not suitable for pencil, charcoal, pastel, chalk, or graphite media ✓ Round corners for safer handling ✓ Notch in top layer for easier handling ✓ Store document in acid-free folder or storage box. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
<p>Flat document larger item requiring extra support</p>	<p>Mylar-cardstock encapsulation Or I-folder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 4 mil mylar ✓ Acid-free, buffered card stock, .010-.025" ✓ Encapsulation for items that need to be viewed from one side only ✓ L-folder to retain access to original ✓ Not suitable for pencil, charcoal, pastel, chalk, or graphite media ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents
<p>Photographs</p>	<p>Unbuffered L-Folder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Store photos away from other materials. ✓ Small photos may be placed in folders made from unbuffered #80 paper. ✓ Large photos may be placed in folders made from acid-free boxboard on one side, unbuffered paper on the front. ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents

Material type	recommended enclosure	enclosure characteristics
Documents in soft media (e.g., charcoal, pastel, pencil)	Covered mat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Acid-free mat for support ✓ Cover mat with acid-free board, hinged at top ✓ No glass or plastic covers ✓ Label on enclosure identifying contents ✓ May be stacked in small groups in map cases or file cabinets.
Colored prints	Mylar encapsulation or L-folder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Unbuffered papers only with color prints ✓ Otherwise directions as above.

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Prepared by Kathy Parker, West Virginia Wesleyan College, and based on a workshop by Jill Deiss, Cat Tail Run Bookbindery.
A New TiLTS Project of the Appalachian College Association Central Library

Plan for Document-Delivery Service Appalachian College Association

- To be useful to ACA libraries, the article delivery service should
 - reduce staff time for the borrowing library
 - not require additional staff time for the lending library
 - not use the OCLC ILL subsystem, which is not available to all ACA libraries
 - e-mail the article directly to the requesting faculty member or student
 - provide an easy way for the borrowing library to track statistics and copyright compliance
 - have an easy-to-access list of journal holdings for participating ACA libraries
 - use Tony Tokens to pay for service
 - be optional for libraries to use
 - not require libraries to lend articles in order to borrow articles
 - provide training for using the service.

- A Web-based ACA Library Union List should
 - be available for anyone to search
 - be searchable by journal title and ISSN
 - provide library name and holdings information (beginning and ending volume/date; major gaps of more than one year)
 - include information from libraries willing to lend articles
 - include links to JSTOR titles available to all ACA libraries
 - include links to open access titles (as provided by ACA libraries)
 - permit the patron to select the library with the appropriate holdings
 - provide a link to the article-request form
 - provide links to ACA library OPACs and full-text journal lists.

- The article-request form should
 - be password-protected so that only ACA libraries or their patrons may use it
 - automatically include the journal title and ISSN information from the Union List
 - include patron information (name, faculty/staff/student, home library, e-mail address), citation information (article title, author, volume, dates, and pages), and citation source
 - require the patron to acknowledge compliance with copyright guidelines
 - remind the patron of borrowing etiquette guidelines (to be developed)

- e-mail the request to the lending library and copy the patron's home library.
- Lending libraries should
- receive a 50 Tony Token credit for adding holdings to the ACA Union List
 - respond to the request within two workdays
 - notify the patron if they cannot fill the request
 - digitize the article
 - e-mail the article directly to the patron *or* post the article to the ILL server and e-mail the patron the access link and password
 - notify the patron's home library that the request has been filled.
- Borrowing libraries should
 - provide their article-request password to faculty and students (optional)
 - maintain data for copyright compliance
 - report the number of articles received from each ACA library at least three times a year so that Tony Tokens can be exchanged.
 - monitor activity to ensure they have enough Tony Tokens to cover the number of articles received.